

Emission of environmental pollutants from oxy-coal combustion in fluidized bed

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Introduction

Oxy-fuel combustion

Fluidized bed

Advantages

- No need of separation and concentration of CO₂
- Retrofit of the current boiler
- Possibility of reduction of NOx and SOx

Disadvantages

- Need of air separation unit (ASU)
- Unknown of NOx and SOx emission behaviors

- High combustion efficiency at low temperature
- Compatible with a wide variety of fuels

Objectives : Understanding NOx & SOx emission behaviors during the Oxy-Coal fluidized bed combustion

- Combustion tests under Air, CO₂-O₂ and Oxy-fuel conditions
- Elucidation of formation behaviors of NO, N₂O, SO₂ and SO₃
- Discussions on NOx and SOx formation/decomposition reactions

Experiment

Proximate analysis[wt.-%-d.b.]			
Volatile Matter	Fixed Carbon	Ash	Moisture
28.2	55.8	16.0	2.2

Ultimate Analysis[wt.-%-d.a.f.]				
C	H	N	S	O
83.19	4.95	1.73	0.21	9.92

Ash composition[%]					
SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO
45.45	30.75	1.30	14.20	3.79	0.92
				P ₂ O ₅	MnO
				1.10	0.18
				V ₂ O ₅	0.03
				SO ₃	1.35

Coal	Coal N				
	Air	CO ₂ -O ₂	Oxy-Fuel		
Atmosphere					
Temperature [K]	973, 1073, 1173				
Bed material particle diameter [μm]	160				
Minimum fluidization velocity [m/s]	0.043				
Bed height [m]	0.16				
u/u _{mf} [-]	4				
Flow ratio of fluidization gas [L/min]	Air 12.8	CO ₂	10.1	Exhaust gas	6.1
		O ₂	2.7	CO ₂	4.3
				O ₂	2.6
Stoichiometric ratio [-] (O ₂ conc.)	1.2				
Sample feed rate [g/min]	1.27				
Dilution ratio [-]	5 (Sample gas : N ₂ = 1:4)				

Results and discussion

NO concentration in the exhaust

Actual NO emission

Actual SO₂ emission

Actual N₂O emission

Actual SO₃ emission

SO₃ concentration

Air ≈ CO₂-O₂ << Oxy-Fuel

Main formation reactions of SO₃

- Promotion of SO₃ formation by oxidation of recirculated SO₂.

- Formation Reaction via HOSO₂.

Conclusions

- Formation of NO was depressed under Oxy-Fuel combustion due to decrease of NCO radical formation
- Formation of NO was depressed under Oxy-Fuel combustion due to H radical formed by CO oxidation
- SO₂ concentration under Oxy-Fuel was higher than that under Air and CO₂-O₂ mode due to the flue gas recirculation.
- SO₃ was produced by formation of HOSO₂ radical formed by reaction of OH with SO₂